

Performance Evaluation of Universities as Groups of Decision Making Units

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Abstract : Universities have different offices such as educational, research, student, administrative, and financial offices. This paper considers universities as groups of decision making units (DMUs) in which DMUs are their offices. This approach gives us with a more just evaluation of universities instead of separate evaluation of the offices of universities. The proposed approach to evaluate group performance of universities is based on common set of weights method in DEA. The suggested method not only can compare groups and measure their efficiencies, but also can calculate the efficiency of units within group and efficiency spread of groups. At last, the suggested method is applied for the analysis of the performance of universities in 14th district of Islamic Azad University as groups under evaluation.

Keywords : common set of weights, group efficiency, performance analysis, spread efficiency.

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